

Response of rice to fertilizers and sitosym applications

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We studied the effect of sitosym combined with different rates of NPKS on irrigated rice (IR42) during 1981-88 wet season. A split-plot design with three replications was used, with sitosym in the main plot and NPKS in the

subplots.

Soil at the experimental site at Ma'rang, Pangkep, has a silty clay texture, pH 5.6, 4 ppm available P (Bray I), CEC 10.5 meq/100 g, and 0.7, 7.6, 4.8 meq/100 g exchangeable K, Ca, Mg, respectively.

Sitosym is claimed to be a complete fertilizer containing Fe, Zn, Cu, Mn, Ca, Mg, S, P, K, protein, and vitamins. Spray application is recommended at panicle initiation at 0.5 liter diluted with

200 liters water/ha. Treatments of NPKS as urea, TSP, KCl, and ammonium sulfate are given in the table.

Application of sitosym did not significantly affect plant height, productive tillers, grain weight, filled grain, or yield. More than 150 kg urea, 100 kg ammonium sulfate, 100 kg triple superphosphate, and 50 kg KCl/ha also did not significantly increase those parameters. □

Response of IR42 to fertilizers and sitosym (S) applications.^a Ma'rang, Pangkep, South Sulawesi, Indonesia, 1988 wet season.

Fertilizer treatment ^b (kg/ha)				Plant height at harvest		Productive tillers (no./hill)		1000-grain wt (g)		Grain yield (t/ha)		Filled grain (%)	
Urea	AS	TSP	KCl	With S	No S	With S	No S	With S	No S	With S	No S	With S	No S
150	100	100	50	105.1	108.5	16	16	22.53	22.00	6.2	5.9	92.0	94.2
150	150	100	50	108.8	110.4	17	16	21.67	22.10	6.0	6.4	93.4	91.9
200	100	100	50	110.6	110.6	14	15	22.20	22.07	6.0	6.2	93.4	92.6
200	100	100	100	108.1	107.2	17	15	22.40	22.27	6.1	6.2	91.3	91.9
200	100	150	100	105.5	109.1	15	15	22.23	22.27	6.0	5.9	92.6	92.9
200	100	200	100	102.5	106.9	16	16	22.27	22.10	6.1	5.8	92.1	92.3
			Mean	106.8	108.8	16	16	22.22	22.13	6.0	6.0	92.6	92.6
			CV (%)										
			(a)	12.1	16.8	3.4	14.8	4.3					
			(b)	3.9	9.2	2.2	8.4	1.4					

^aTests of means showed nonsignificant effects. Seeds and grains were at 14% moisture content. ^bUrea: 45% N, TSP: triple superphosphate (45% P₂O₅), AS: ammonium sulfate (20% N, 24% S), KCl: 60% K₂O.

Effect on rice of phorate at different N levels

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We studied the effect on rainfed rice of phorate at varying levels of N in Feb-Jun 1983. Phorate is an organophosphate insecticide (0,0-Diethyl S-[(ethylthio) methyl] phosphorodithioate) available as 10% granules. At 1 kg ai/ha, it controls many rice pests through a combination of systemic, contact, and fumigant insecticidal action.

The experiment was laid out in a factorial combination of 3 levels of N (0, 60, and 90 kg N/ha as urea) and 4 levels of phorate (0, 1.0, 2.0, and 3.0 kg ai/ha)

in a randomized block design with 4 replications. The soil at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU) (11°N, 77°E, and 427 m above mean sea level) was a Vertisoi (clay loam) containing 1.0% organic C, 99-8.0-254 ppm available NPK, 0.7 ppm DTPA extractable Zn, with pH 8.2 and EC 0.3 dS/m. Test variety was IR20. All plots were uniformly fertilized and kept insect free. Standard management practices were followed.

Phorate (10% granules) was incorporated at planting to ensure minimum loss. N as urea was applied in 3 splits: 50% basal, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation.

Tiller number, leaf area index, root weight, root volume, and grain yield (see table) increased with N application up to 90 kg/ha and phorate application up to 2.0 kg ai/ha. This indicates growth-

Grain yield of IR20 rice as influenced by phorate and N level. TNAU, Coimbatore, India, 1983.

N levels (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha) at phorate levels (kg ai/ha) of				Mean yield (t/ha)
	0	1	2	3	
0	2.3	3.5	3.9	3.3	3.4
60	4.2	3.6	3.8	5.3	4.2
90	4.2	5.4	5.4	4.8	5.0
Mean	3.6	4.1	4.4	4.5	
		<i>SEm</i> ±		<i>LSD</i> (0.05)	
Nitrogen (N)		0.16		0.46	
Phorate (P)		0.26		0.66	
N × P		0.40		1.06	

stimulating effects of phorate on rice and a synergistic phorate-N interaction.

Based on grain yield increase: costs ratio (1 kg phorate 10% granule: US\$2.50; 1 kg N:US\$0.50; application at US\$2.90/laborer), 90 kg N/ha and 1.0 kg ai phorate/ha is optimum. □